

“A SHINING STAR”

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Abstract. In this article, there is a private conversation with the little star Miyasar Dauletbaeva, who is known to our people for her unique performance, and her family members, way, achievements in the genre of pop music, difficulties in this field are discussed.

Key words: Music, contest, song musical instruments, teacher, student, plan.

“СИЯЮЩАЯ ЗВЕЗДА”

Аннотация. В этой статье идет приватная беседа с маленькой звездой Миясар Даулетбаевой, которая известна нашему народу своим уникальным исполнением, и членами ее семьи, обсуждаются путь, достижения в жанре поп-музыки, трудности на этом поприще.

Ключевые слова: музыка, конкурс, песенные музыкальные инструменты, учитель, ученик, план.

Music is type of musical art great importance in the development of a person in our cultural life, creating a high level of emotion in a person and shaping the vision of the cultural world. Also, has the opportunity to have a strong influence on the human soul.

Abu Nasr Farabi a scholar of our national cultural said that “A work of simple words fiction written incoherently was beneficial to the health of the body” And Saadiy Sheraziy said “Music is a satellite of the human soul”

Music is considered to be an emotional powerful active developer that has quick effect on a person the first music we hear from our mothers along with human music is “Lullaby” through which we enjoy music a lifetime and gain strength.

Music is an integral part of the human soul, and in order to enjoy it, a person must be able to feel a pure beauty with a high civilized heart, and in his soul he must have a love for the motherland.

We did not give up our thoughts and reflections on music. Next to you the human being who wants to introduce the musical art direction to our people, who have achieved several achievements is known for his singing and the little light coming bright as the star Miyasar Dauletbaeva.

On October 3, 2006, in the city of Nukus, the Dauletbaev’s family gave birth to a future starlet named Miyasar. Her passion for the world of music began as early as childhood. The main reason why Miyasar has entered this direction is his family members.

Her father Allamuratov Qilishbay, a role model of starlet, received his training in the vocal direction of the department of “National performance” at the current Nukus specialized school of culture between 1992 and 1996, he composed the “National performance skills” section at Children’s music school N 2. He was then one of the students of Karakalpak State University in 2004-2007. After completing his studies well he has been teaching a number of students in the current school of culture, the first reading lesson in the direction of music in the same year.

This is due to the respect of a person for our national values not only at work, but at the same time also to his children in the family circle who played the National Music of our people live on their own and also told the legends associated with the history of the origin of these music. It was by showing that their dignity was great that children’s love and affection for the direction of music helped them awaken. At the same time he was also making duwtar and making musical instruments. His work also had a good effect on his children. The reason is that when they are little, they see musical instruments in their home, and by studying their structure and playing them, they also get to know others from the folk singer.

Her mother Sapargul Basherova is very kind person who gave birth to Miyasar, had a strong interest in playing the also moynaq duwtar, considered the national musical instrument of Karakalpak from a young age. It was during this time that his choice of this direction was opposed by his parents. But despite this, her brother Turganbay Qurbanov, began to teach her the secrets of baqsishiliq as her mentor.

Miyasar’s mother, like her father, studied at the current “Nukus specialized school of culture in the baqsishiliq direction of the “National Performanse” department. She has been a teacher at the N12 children’s music school named after Amet baqsi since 1996.

Her lovely voice got Miyasar into her heart with “Lullaby”. For this reason, it can also be said that it is the owner of the innate talent.

While her mother has trained hundreds of disciples so far, Miyasar Dauletbaeva is among them. Mother and child work on themselves not only at school, but also at home, and soon learned to correct mistakes and shortcomings. So it can be said that your mother played a big role in the achievement of the strong talent.

One of Miyasar’s supporters is her caring and kind brother Talgat Dauletbaev. We know this person. The reason is that you can see. Miyasar as a guitarist and pianist next to her in the songs she performs on every stage. He even knew how to play and tune the duwtar at the age of 4. He devoted most of his life to this music. Since childhood, Talgat went to music school with his mother and learned to play the girjek musical instrument along with the dutar. He won many competitions. He won many competition.

He graduated from the music school majoring in duwtar and girjek, but he also knew how to play stringed instruments such as the violin, guitar, and rubob. In 2011-2014, Miyasar’s brother studied “Music theory” at the current Nukus specialized culture school. After that, he became interested in composing songs, and in 2014-2018 he successfully graduated from the faculty of Composition of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan. In 2020-2022, he graduated from the graduate department of the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz and since this year he has been working at the Nukus branch of the Uzbekistan State Conservatory.

Gulkhumor Dauletbaeva, Miyasar's closest and confident friend, is also a representative of this musical direction. She graduated from the music school N12 named after Amet Jaqsi along with Miyasar, majoring in piano. Later, she also studied "Music Theory" at the current Nukus Specialized Culture school in 2020-2022. Currently, Gulkhumor is a 2nd year student of the Faculty of Musical arts of the Nukus branch of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan. Her sister also played an important role in Miyasar's success, because she grew up playing with Miyasar and was a strong motivator for him in good and bad days.

As for Miyasar herself, as we mentioned above, she was interested in music from a young age. She went to music school together with her mother and was in the lively life there and soon began to study in the music department. The young talent was interested in playing the girjek in addition to the duwtar, actively participated in solfeggio and choir lessons. After attending choir lessons, she began to love singing, and then her parents asked her to enroll in the vocal academy. Looking positively at her daughter's choice, her parents sent Miyasar to Rinat Dawirkanov's class in 2015. New doors are starting to open for the future star in the world of music, she participated in many competition's and won high places.

By the way, in 2017 she became a laureate at the "Kamalak Yulduzlari" Children's creative festival, and in 2019, she won the 1st place at the Karakalpak stage of the "Akademik ham Estrada ijrochilari tanlovi" The year 2020 was a difficult time for the whole world, because the virus "Covid19" appeared on earth, for which a cure has not yet been found and medicine is still unknown. In the same year, this virus entered our country, and our president introduced a quarantine period in our republic in order to prevent the situations from getting worse. In order not to waste time in quarantine, Miyasar participated in several about this, the best performer in the 2020 "Jas gitarashi" competition held by the council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan of the Youth union of uzbeks on the occasion of the "Jaslar kuni "On June 30" the Russian Federation, the city of Moscow education and was awarded with 2nd level diplomas in the nomination "Vokalno- xorovoe tvorchestvo" ("Вокально- хоровое творчество ") within the international Festival of Russian language held by the department of science.

A student, Miyasar showed interested in Russian literature as well as and participated in several international competitions 2020 with the 1st degree diploma at the international Russian language online festival for young children, teenagers and young adults named "Puteshestvie v stranu russkogo yazika" ("Путешествие в страну русского языка", " Живое классика ") was with diplomas for winning the school and district stages of the international young readers competition. At the end of that year, the future star took part in the selection stage of the "The cover up kids" project held by the "zo'r TV" television and radio company of Tashkent with her brother and joined Yorqinxoja Umarov's group. If this project had 10 stages, it can be said that Miyasar sang in 10 different non-repeating genres.

Despite her young age, she listened to the words of Yo'rqinxo'ja who was her teacher, and got along very well with the musicians. Because of her demandingness, the talented Miyasar won the diploma and trophy as the 1st place holder in this project. After this project, in order to adequately reward the work done in 2020 the Youth Affairs Agency of Uzbekistan received a diploma and a statuette in the nomination "Jildin en talantli jasi" in the "Xoshamet 2020" award program held by the youth association of the department of the Republic of Karakalpaqstan

entered. 2021 was one of the most successful years for Miyassar in this creative career. In the same year, she participated well in the variety section of the final stage of the festival “Respublika jaslar hawazi” organized by the Uzbek Youth Affairs Agency, the Uzbek Youth Association and received a 2nd degree diploma with the situation “Taxsin 2021” in order to reward her sacrifices “Umid uchquni” according to the 450th meeting of Board of Directions of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, a participant of the “Chegarasiz” project of the Uzbek Youth Affairs Agency, on August 30, 2021 was awarded with bronze badge.

Well, 2022 was a year full of great achievements for Miyasar. This year, she won the “Ekinshi ana tilim – qaraqalpaq tili” essay contest organized by the Ministry of public Education of Karakalpakstan, the 1st level diplomas in the “G’azelxanliq” contest organized by the Ministry of Republic Education of Karakalpakstan. The Republic of Uzbek organized by the Ministry of culture “san’atim senga, abod yurtim” with a 2nd level diploma in the competition, with a 1st level diploma in the international “Shukufaxoi-Paytaxt” organized in Dushanbe republic of Tajikistan and “Festival talantov” organized by the “Intali balalar” International Society (Фестивал талантов”) was awarded the Grand Prix at the VII International selection.

In October 2022, Miyasar’s participation in the “Xon Saray Music” contest was a big turning point in the young girl’s life. The reason is that at the beginning of 2023, after “Xon Saroy music” and especially “Top Music” Miyasar was approved for the main competition stages. Out of the first 30 people, 20 people were selected, including the top ten out of 20 was very hard for Miyasar. The reason is that on that day the wedding of her brother, Talgat Dauletbaev was scheduled. Now she had to choose either the wedding or staying at the competition. Not only Miyasar, but all her family members worried because of the situation. Since Miyasar’s brother was an expert in the field of culture, they agreed to participate in the project after consulting each other. However, Miyasar had one choice. She also told her brother: “If I miss the wedding, or I am not selected to the top ten, I won’t sing never again”.

Her brother supported her and expressed his confidence in hers. That difficult day that we have been waiting for has arrived. Wedding in Nukus, Competition in Tashkent. It was reported that Alisher Uzatov was celebrating her wedding and that Miyasar was in the top twelve. During the project, she sang the songs of Kumush Razzakova, Sevgi Takhmineva, “Setora” group and “Alo” group of Uzbek pop music. She was able to perfectly perform the songs of Christina Aguilera, Ruslana, Miriam Fares and Selena Gomes from the world pop. With this, we have reached the final stage of this project, which lasted for less than a year. In the final participant had feelings of panic and fear, including Miyasar. Family members were there to support her. After the performance of the participants, we have reached the, most difficult time. The votes of each participant during the project were counted on the monitor.

The thing that scared us the most was that Miyasar’s collected voice rose slowly compared to other participants until the last second. But the number of votes collected in those last seconds quickly increased and Miyasar became the 1st place, which made all the viewers happy. Now, she is gifting the car and the house to her family. Today, the young talent miyasar dauletbaeva chose to study 11th grade in Tashkent in order to further develop her creativity. She has many goals. I would have to write a book to tell them all. Therefore, we will keep them confidential.

By the way, this little star is going on a trip to Georgia in the next few days. We wish her a good trip and success in her creativity.

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